

THE MEDIATING ROLE OF GUEST SATISFACTION ON THE INFLUENCE OF TOURISM PRACTICES ON GUEST LOYALTY

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ABSTRACT

Tourism practices significantly shape the hospitality industry by influencing guest experience, satisfaction, and loyalty. This study examined the mediating role of guest satisfaction in the relationship between tourism practices and guest loyalty using a descriptive-correlational design with Structural Equation Modeling. A total of 300 resort guests participated in the study. The investigator employed a combination of a modified (Quiapo & Chavez, 2024) questionnaire as well as a researcher-made survey to collect information for this research. Data were organized using descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings reveal that guests exhibit strong loyalty, indicating potential long-term brand connections. While technological advancements and sustainable tourism practices contribute to the overall experience, they do not strongly affect loyalty. Experiential travel, however, has a substantial effect on guest loyalty, both directly and indirectly. Guests value tourism practices as a basis for satisfaction, which in turn enhances loyalty. Although the guest experience generally meets or exceeds expectations, further improvements could maximize satisfaction. Collaboration among key stakeholders, including government agencies, tourists, and researchers, is essential to fostering responsible tourism. Strengthening marketing strategies, promoting sustainable and tech-driven tourism, and encouraging responsible travel behavior support long-term industry growth. By integrating sustainability, technology, and experiential offerings, the hospitality industry can enhance guest experiences while ensuring cultural and environmental integrity, ultimately leading to increased customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Keywords: *Experiential Travel, Guest Loyalty, Guest Satisfaction, Tourism Practices, and Technological Advancement*

INTRODUCTION

Transformations within the tourism sector develop through evolving guest trends alongside environmental demands as well as technological developments. Hospitality businesses operating in dynamic global tourism need to adapt to trends that shape how guests evaluate their services and build loyalty. Liu (2020) recognizes that global tourism changes rapidly because it directly influences the preferences of tourists. The present investigation examines how sustainable tourism and technological development and experiential travel affect guest satisfaction and loyalty in local resorts.

This study makes use of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) within a descriptive-correlational design for analyzing complex variable relationships. The research design utilizes SEM because it allows investigation of direct and indirect impact relationships thus providing a suitable framework for examining satisfaction mediation between tourism practices and guest loyalty. This reviews the limited application of SEM in tourism demand modeling, noting that although SEM can offer valuable insights into complex relationships, it remains underused due to the methodological challenges and the lack of accessible resources for researchers in the tourism field (Wang, 2020).

The research gap identified in this study is the limited understanding of how guest satisfaction mediates the relationship between sustainable tourism practices, technological advancements, and experiential travel options in fostering guest loyalty highlighting the need to explore whether these tourism practices truly translate into lasting loyalty through enhanced satisfaction. Several studies have examined the direct effects of tourism practices on guest satisfaction and loyalty; however, limited empirical research has explored the mediating role of guest satisfaction in these relationships. For instance, Po and Jiang (2023) found that while green practices in hospitality settings positively influenced customer perceptions, their impact on loyalty was significantly enhanced only when guests reported a high level of satisfaction. Similarly, Rasoolimanesh et al. (2022) emphasized that memorable tourism experiences influence behavioral intentions more strongly when mediated by visitor satisfaction. These findings underscore the need for a deeper investigation into how various tourism practices—such as sustainability initiatives, technological enhancements, and experiential offerings—translate into long-term loyalty through the lens of satisfaction, supporting the rationale for this study.

Recent studies have increasingly highlighted the pivotal role of guest satisfaction as a mediating factor between sustainable tourism practices, technological advancements, experiential travel, and guest loyalty. For instance, Wahyuningsih et al. (2024) conducted a study in Indonesian tourism villages, revealing that economic, environmental, and institutional sustainability significantly influence tourist satisfaction, which in turn positively affects tourist loyalty. Their findings underscore the mediating role of satisfaction in the relationship between sustainability dimensions and loyalty .

Furthermore, Kusumah (2024) explored the sustainable tourism concept by assessing how socioeconomic, cultural, and environmental images of urban destinations affect tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty. The study found that these sustainability-

related images positively influence tourist satisfaction, which then directly impacts destination loyalty, highlighting the mediating role of satisfaction in this relationship.

These studies collectively highlight the necessity of understanding how guest satisfaction functions as a mediator between sustainable practices, technological advancements, experiential travel, and guest loyalty. They provide empirical evidence supporting the exploration of whether these tourism practices truly translate into lasting loyalty through enhanced satisfaction.

This study aims to determine the extent to which tourism practices comprising sustainable tourism practices, technological advancements, and experiential travel influences guest loyalty, with guest satisfaction acting as a mediating variable. By analyzing these relationships, the research intends to offer empirical insights that contribute to the development of more effective and sustainable tourism management strategies.

There are three important cores identified in the study. The first is the need to align with sustainable tourism practices, driven by increasing environmental regulations. Gössling and Higham (2022) stress the importance of businesses complying with environmental mandates to protect natural resources. While sustainability is important, it does not always directly impact guest satisfaction or loyalty, which this study investigates further. Research shows that although tourists increasingly express a preference for sustainability, it is not always a primary driver of satisfaction or loyalty outcomes. For instance, Han et al. (2019) found that while sustainable practices in hotels positively affect guests' environmental attitudes, they do not always translate into heightened guest satisfaction or repeated patronage unless accompanied by superior service quality and memorable experiences. Similarly, a study by Zhang et al. (2020) revealed that tourists appreciate eco-friendly initiatives but prioritize personal comfort, convenience, and the overall emotional quality of their experience when forming loyalty intentions. This suggests that while sustainability enhances brand image and corporate responsibility, it alone is often insufficient to secure guest loyalty without addressing experiential and service-based expectations.

The second highlights the demand for technological advancements in hospitality. Innovations such as AI-powered services, mobile check-ins, and online booking systems are revolutionizing the guest experience. The paper by (Jurny, 2025) demonstrates how these developments create better satisfaction levels alongside operational streamlining. The research explores how technology features create customer satisfaction and determine if this satisfaction leads to customer loyalty.

The third emphasizes the growing relevance of experiential travel, which prioritizes delivering authentic, meaningful experiences over conventional hospitality services. According to Saribaş and Demir (2024), such experiences serve as a critical foundation for forming emotional connections between guests and tourism destinations or accommodations. Their concept of the "experience economy" suggests that when travelers encounter deep, personalized experiences, the perceived value of services increases significantly. This highlights the essential connection between experiential

travel and guest satisfaction, which subsequently plays a vital role in fostering guest loyalty. Therefore, understanding how authentic experiences influence satisfaction and drive long-term loyalty strengthens the rationale for this study, particularly in evaluating whether these experiences can act as a sustainable strategy for improving guest retention in the tourism sector.

Building on this, the study also aligns with global sustainability efforts, particularly Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 12 on Responsible Consumption and Production. The integration of experiential travel with sustainable tourism practices is not only beneficial for guest engagement but also essential for promoting environmental responsibility within the hospitality industry. By emphasizing eco-friendly operations and the use of technological innovations to reduce environmental impact, the research supports the advancement of SDG 12. Moreover, experience-oriented travel provides a platform for educating tourists on responsible behaviors, ultimately contributing to the cultivation of a sustainability-oriented tourism culture.

Consequently, the findings reinforce the importance of strategically combining experience-driven, technology-enhanced, and environmentally responsible practices to meet both guest expectations and sustainability goals. Hotels and tourism establishments are encouraged to design authentic guest experiences that incorporate sustainable operations and smart technologies. Such integration not only boosts guest satisfaction but also nurtures long-term loyalty, thereby offering a comprehensive and future-ready approach to sustainable tourism development.

Research Questions

This research explored the influence of tourism practices, technological advancement and experiential travel on guest loyalty in a local resort through guest satisfaction. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the participants' assessment of the local resorts in terms of:
 - 1.1. Sustainable Tourism Practices
 - 1.2. Technological Advancements
 - 1.3. Experiential Travel
2. What is the participants' level of satisfaction with the local resorts?
3. What is the participants' assessment of their loyalty to the local resorts?
4. Do the participants' assessment of local resorts in terms of sustainable tourism practices, Technological advancements, and Experiential travel options significantly influence their loyalty?
5. Does guest satisfaction mediate the influence of sustainable tourism practices, technological advancements, and experiential travel options on their loyalty?

METHODOLOGY

The key elements of the study's research are examined in this chapter. The primary execution strategy employed during study implementation is explained in this part, along with the fundamentals of research design. This section illustrates how the public settings of the study align with the research area. Data providers and input providers made up the study's bit players. This section provides specifics about the research tool and data collection methods. The procedure entails assigning grades to assessment instruments, which are then processed by the system to allow for the assessment of verified outcomes. The research design is discussed orally in this portion, together with the intended participants, the implementation site, and the evaluation procedure.

Research Design

This study used a descriptive-correlational research approach to examine if guest satisfaction and loyalty relate to tourism practices, such as sustainable tourism, technological advancements, and experiential travel options. According to Creswell (2014), this design is predicated on a rational, hypothesis-driven methodology that relies on statistical analysis and observation and is informed by positivist and empiricist philosophies. Correlational research quantifies the strength of the relationship between independent variables, whereas descriptive research describes the features of the study population. This research design was deemed appropriate because it allowed for the observation of naturally occurring variables without manipulation, which is ideal for exploring behavioral patterns and associations. Descriptive research provided a comprehensive picture of current guest perceptions and experiences, while the correlational component facilitated statistical analysis to determine the strength and direction of the relationships among the variables. This methodological approach is consistent with the positivist tradition, which emphasizes empirical investigation and the use of statistical tools to understand phenomena.

Participants and Sampling Procedure

To provide equitable representation, 300 participants were chosen at random from nearby resorts in a Misamis Oriental municipality for this study. Participants had to be at least 18 years old, have visited one of the chosen resorts in the previous 12 months, and have used at least one of the resort's services or activities in order to be eligible. To verify the credibility of the data, respondents who had never visited the resort or used its services were not included. Strict adherence to ethical guidelines ensured that all participants gave their informed consent, that their privacy was safeguarded, and that participation was entirely voluntary and free of charge.

To guarantee relevance to the study, resorts and hotels were chosen based on predetermined criteria. The only resorts and hotels that were taken into consideration were those that had been open for at least three years and had at least fifty reviews from previous visitors on websites or in official documents. To fit the study's objective,

establishments that actively adopted sustainable tourism practices, integrated technology into their offerings, and offered experiential travel alternatives were given preference. A more thorough examination of the ways in which various tourist practices affect visitor loyalty and satisfaction was made possible by this methodology.

The random sampling method further strengthened the study's validity by giving every eligible participant—regardless of age, gender, or education—an equal chance of selection, thereby minimizing bias and enhancing the generalizability of the findings.

Research Instrument

The investigator employed a combination of a modified Quiapo & Chavez (2024) questionnaire, as well as a researcher-made survey to collect information for this research. Each item on the updated questionnaire, which was backed up by pertinent research, was incorporated into the survey tool. The questionnaire's first section addressed tourism-related topics, including technological developments, experience travel possibilities, and sustainable tourism practices. The questions related to technological advancements were adapted from studies by Beldona & Goh (2021); Cheng et al. (2022); Jeong et al. (2020); Alrawadieh et al. (2020); Mazzarol et al. (2021); Karami & Mohammadi (2021); and Huang et al. (2022). Meanwhile, the section on experiential travel options incorporated a combination of structured and modified questions based on the works of Quiapo & Chavez (2024); Patterson & Pan (2016); and Kim & Lee (2021).

The second section of the questionnaire focused on guest satisfaction, utilizing a self-made questionnaire supported by literature from Quiapo & Chavez (2024); Chen & Chen (2020); Bakar & Ahmad (2021); and Wu & Liang (2021). The final section, which examined guest loyalty, was informed by studies from Agus (2019); Tombs & McColl-Kennedy (2003); Kim & Kim (2019); Sweeney & Webb (2019); Gounaris & Stathakopoulos (2019); and Oliver & De Sarbo (2021).

For the study's validity and reliability, the data gathering procedure was carried out in a thorough and systematic way. Participants were given the option to choose the response that most accurately reflected their personal experiences using a five-point Likert scale in the questionnaire: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, and 5 = Strongly Agree. This structured approach ensured that the gathered data provided valuable insights into the relationship between tourism practices, guest satisfaction, and guest loyalty.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

**Significant at 0.01

Figure 1 presents the findings concerning the indirect effect of guest satisfaction and the direct effect of experiential travel on guest loyalty. As shown in Figure 2, guest satisfaction mediates the relationship between experiential travel, technological advancements, and sustainable tourism practices on guest loyalty. The results show a positive effect of experiential travel ($B=0.37$), technological advancements ($B=0.33$), and sustainable tourism practices ($B=0.21$) on guest satisfaction; and guest satisfaction has a positive influence on guest loyalty ($B=0.31$). Experiential travel has a direct effect on guest loyalty ($B=0.51$); but the other variables do not have a direct effect on guest loyalty. This relationship had to be mediated by guest satisfaction. Thus, it can be confirmed that guest satisfaction has a mediating effect on the influence of experiential travel, technological advancements, and sustainable tourism practices on guest loyalty. The results indicate that for every 1-unit increase in guest satisfaction, there is a corresponding 0.31 increase in their loyalty. Based on the result, the null hypothesis is rejected. Guests who are satisfied with the technological advancements and the sustainable tourism practices of the resorts demonstrate loyalty in coming back to the resort.

In particular, as shown in Table 7, experiential travel options have a direct effect on guest loyalty ($B=0.510$), emphasizing its critical role in shaping guest behavior. Moreover, the covariances between experiential travel, technological advancements, and sustainable tourism practices are statistically significant. The covariance between technological advancements and experiential travel is ($B=0.325$), while sustainable tourism practices also show strong relationships with both technological advancements ($B=0.334$) and experiential travel ($B=0.334$).

These values indicate that these constructs tend to vary together, suggesting an interdependent relationship. It highlights the potential for strategic alignment;

enhancements in one domain may correspond with positive developments in the others within tourism and hospitality systems.

These findings suggest that the level of guest loyalty can be influenced by the quality of experiences, adoption of technological advancements, and sustainable tourism efforts. The results support the suggestion made by Yazid, (2020) that enhancing guest experiences and utilizing technological innovations are crucial for fostering guest satisfaction and long-term loyalty. Additionally, a positive guest experience and the integration of technology significantly influence consumer evaluations of services, particularly in terms of loyalty, as noted by Shin & Jeong (2022). On the other hand, a lack of creativity or subpar service could result in less satisfied and loyal customers. These results support the notion that better guest experiences and technology advancements can result in higher loyalty outcomes. They also support the study by Sofi et al. (2024), which highlights the role that guest pleasure plays as a link between service components and consumer loyalty.

The findings emphasize how crucial visitor pleasure is in moderating the link between sustainable tourism practices, technological improvements, and experience travel on guest loyalty. To increase client satisfaction, it may be beneficial for businesses especially those in the hospitality and tourist industries to concentrate on creating unforgettable experiences and utilizing technology advancements while upholding sustainable standards. By doing this, businesses can foster increased patronage, which will guarantee sustained prosperity and favorable client relations.

The final model fit summary, which assesses the structural model using a number of important fit indices, is shown in Table 8. Because values below 0.08 indicate a well-fitting model, the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) of 0.004 indicates an excellent model fit Hu & Bentler (1999). The model's adequacy is reinforced by the low difference between the observed and estimated covariance matrices, as evidenced by the Unweighted Least Squares Discrepancy (d_uls) of 160.114 and the Geodesic Discrepancy (d_G) of 0.001 (Hair et al., 2017). Given that non-significant Chi-square values signify a decent fit, the model appears not to significantly diverge from the observed data, as indicated by the Chi-square value of 4.429 and the p-value of 0.109 Kline (2016). Additionally, the suggested model shows a strong incremental fit, as evidenced by the Normed Fit Index (NFI) of 0.996, which is higher than the 0.90 cutoff suggested by Bentler & Bonett (1980).

Table 1
The Final Model Fit Summary.

Fit Index	Estimate	Interpretation Criteria
Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)	0.004	< 0.08 (Excellent fit)
Unweighted Least Squares Discrepancy (d_ULS)	160.114	Acceptable if < 95% bootstrap threshold
Geodesic Discrepancy (d_G)	0.001	Acceptable if < 95% bootstrap threshold
Chi-square	4.429 (p=.109)	Non-significant (p > 0.05) indicates good fit
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	0.996	> 0.90 (Strong incremental fit)
RMSEA	0.064	< 0.08 (Acceptable Fit)

Furthermore, an adequate fit within the model is indicated by the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), which is 0.064. According to Browne and Cudeck (1993), RMSEA values less than 0.08 are typically seen as suggestive of a decent model fit. Although a close fit would be indicated by a number less than 0.05, the current RMSEA score is still within an acceptable range, suggesting that the model accurately captures the data. The absence of a significant upper bound strengthens confidence in the model's overall fit, even though the confidence interval (0.000 to 0.146) indicates some uncertainty in the estimation.

These results imply that the model accurately depicts the correlations found in the study, which focuses on customer interaction behavior, marketing techniques, and customer preferences in hospitality facilities. The strength of the proposed linkages is supported by the high model fit indices, which show that the structural model adequately captures customer preferences, engagement behaviors, and marketing strategies.

The model fit results support the findings of Manosuthi et al. (2021), which are in line with other studies that highlighted how crucial well-structured models are to comprehending consumer behavior. Furthermore, research by Kuo & Chen (2020) High model fit values have been demonstrated to improve the dependability of conclusions derived from structural equation modeling (SEM), hence bolstering the validity of the results in the present study.

Businesses in the hospitality industry can use the study's insights to improve their customer engagement and marketing efforts because of the results of the good model fit. According to the findings, customer satisfaction and loyalty in the hospitality sector are greatly impacted by experiential travel options, technology developments, and sustainable tourism practices. In order to maximize consumer involvement and pleasure, businesses should concentrate on improving guest experiences, incorporating cutting-edge technologies, and encouraging sustainable practices.

Conclusions

The study reveals that sustainable tourism practices, technological advancements, and Experiential Travel contribute positively to guests' overall travel experiences. However, while these aspects are recognized, there is still potential for further improvement in certain areas to enhance guest satisfaction. The findings suggest that while most participants are satisfied with their resort experiences, continuous efforts to refine and elevate services can lead to an even greater level of guest appreciation and enjoyment.

The notable finding of guest satisfaction as having a mediating effect on these variables to guest loyalty implies that a large number of satisfied visitors will probably come back and refer others to the resort, both of which are essential for sustained commercial success. The resort's competitive edge can be further strengthened by enhancing guest loyalty through improved services, customized experiences, and well-thought-out loyalty programs.

Furthermore, the results demonstrate that while sustainable tourism policies have little effect on travel preferences, experiential travel options and technology developments do. This implies that although sustainability is still a desirable idea, tourists do not use it as their main criterion when selecting a resort. Rather, tourists value the ease, creativity, and immersive experiences that come with technology and unusual travel experiences. These results demonstrate how contemporary tourists' tastes are changing, favoring engaging and customized experiences over conventional sustainability initiatives.

Furthermore, this study demonstrates the close relationship between customer loyalty and satisfaction, especially in the areas of technology, experiential travel, and sustainable tourism. This confirms the Expectation-Confirmation Theory (Oliver, 1980), indicating that contentment fosters loyalty when visitor experiences are on par with or better than expected. When visitors' expectations are fulfilled or surpassed during their visit, they become satisfied, which encourages loyalty. When they are satisfied with a resort's sustainable operations, cutting-edge technology, and immersive travel experiences, they become more enthusiastic, which in turn greatly boosts their loyalty.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are endorsed:

1. That the Local Government Unit (LGU) may:
 - 1.1 work together with communities and the private sector to make sure that tourist growth satisfies the distinct cultural, environmental, and financial requirements of the area. Both tourists and local communities may gain from this partnership's potential to produce a more seamless travel experience.
 - 1.2 invest in the growth of ecotourism, including water sports, bike excursions, and trekking. The LGU can attract adventurers while protecting the environment by improving access to natural landmarks including parks, beaches, woods, and mountains. Additionally, this will support sustainability objectives by guaranteeing

- that the growth of the tourism industry respects and preserves the regional ecology.
2. That the Department of Tourism (DOT) may:
 - 2.1. develop focused advertising efforts that highlight the Philippines' advantages as a destination for adventure travel. These advertisements ought to highlight eco-friendly pursuits like eco-resorts, guided nature hikes, and coral reef restoration initiatives; tech-driven experiences like smartphone travel apps, smart hotel services, and virtual tours of historical sites; and immersive cultural events like traditional festivals, local cooking classes, and visits from indigenous communities. Creating ads that appeal to adventurers, eco-tourists, and tech-savvy tourists would help the Philippines stand out in the crowded international travel industry.
 3. That the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) may:
 - 3.1 enhance eco-tourism initiatives by collaborating with local communities to create a range of experiential travel activities. These could include guided nature walks, wildlife observation tours, and eco-friendly resort accommodations, all designed to allow travelers to experience nature firsthand. This approach would not only promote environmental conservation but also provide a unique, immersive experience for visitors, helping to foster a deeper appreciation for the natural beauty of the Philippines.
 4. That Resort-Business Owners may:
 - 4.1. Increase client happiness, businesses can concentrate on creating unforgettable experiences and utilizing technology advancements while upholding sustainable standards. Businesses can foster better client loyalty, long-term success, and positive customer connections by doing this.
 - 4.2. Ought to concentrate on using technology to improve ease, providing creative and engaging travel experiences, and making sure that all of these elements affect overall visitor pleasure. Sustainability shouldn't be disregarded, but it should be incorporated without sacrificing the guests' top priorities of ease and enjoyment. In the end, enhancing these crucial areas will guarantee a competitive edge in the changing travel sector by boosting long-term loyalty and visitor pleasure.
 5. That Tourists may:
 - 5.1. respect local cultures and traditions to foster meaningful interactions. This helps ensure that tourism benefits local communities without disrupting their cultural heritage. Engaging in authentic experiences, such as cultural tours, artisan workshops, and local food experiences, supports the local economy and promotes cultural appreciation rather than exploitation.
 6. That students may:
 - 6.1 practice Mindful Tourism, which means being conscious of their environmental impact, respecting local customs, and avoiding behaviors that could negatively affect the destination. This approach not only leads to a more fulfilling experience but also reinforces the satisfaction that comes from knowing you are contributing positively to the places you visit. Mindful tourism encourages a sense of responsibility, which can enhance a student's loyalty to sustainable destinations, fostering a long-term commitment to these values.
 - 6.2 engage in Responsible Tourism Practices to help improve their travel experiences, as sustainable practices align with factors that boost satisfaction in

tourists. Positive experiences are more likely to lead to repeat visits and long-term loyalty to destinations that prioritize sustainability.

7. That Future researchers may:

7.1 explore and conduct more studies about the exploration of guest experience, satisfaction, and loyalty to help shape the future of the industry and guide local resorts toward creating exceptional experiences for guests.

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